

Effect Of Normal And Oblique Impact Damages On The Strength Degradation Of Composite Laminates

S. T. Jenq¹, S. B. Wang², and J. D. Wu²
Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics
National Cheng Kung University, Tainan, Taiwan, R.O.C.

ABSTRACT

The impact residual strength of a S-glass/epoxy (Fiberite Hy-E 9134B) laminate struck by a blunt or tip-ended projectile in the normal and oblique incidence are reported in this paper. Three different types of specimens, i.e. $[0]_1$, $[0_5/90_5/0_5]$, and $[(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_s$ laminates, are studied. The corresponding tensile residual strength of impacted specimens are obtained experimentally. Effect of impact energy, projectile's incident angles, shape of penetrators, and the layup of the composite laminates on the strength degradation are discussed. The ballistic limit of composite specimens is also reported.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the composite laminated structures have been widely used in many areas, such as aerospace and automotive industries, because of their superior strength and light weight compared to those of a metallic structures. Impact damage problems have been one of the interesting topics needed to be studied in order to understand the impact resistance of highly stressed structures.

Many related works have been published in the past to describe the transient behaviors of composite laminates subject to impulsive loading^(1,2,3,4,5), the impact damage characterization^(6,7,8,9,10,11). It is found that impact damage modes can be classified as indentation, fiber breakage, matrix cracking, debonding and delamination. These damages may result in strength degradation of composite laminates. Several works^(12,13,14,15) have reported the effect of impact damages on the residual strength of composite laminates. Many of these

¹ Associate Professor

² Graduate Assistant

results are based on test findings when the targets are normally struck by a penetrator at low velocity range.

In this paper, two types of penetrators, i.e. blunt and tip-ended cylindrical shapes, are used to fire against composite laminates made of S-glass/epoxy (Fiberite 9134B). Both normal and oblique impact tests have been performed. The impact residual strength is also found using a MTS tester. Experimental findings are presented and the ballistic limit is also reported here. A finite element code in conjunction with Tsai-Wu failure criterion and a strength degradation model is developed also to predict residual strength and stress-strain curve of damaged composite laminates but not presented here.

EXPEIRMENTAL SETUP AND PROCEDURES

In this work the composite targets are made of S-glass/epoxy uni-directional pre-preg tape (Fiberite Hy-E 9134B). Hot press and vacuum bag are used to cure composite laminate. The rectangular specimen (25.4 cm by 2.54 cm) is rigidly clamped on both ends. Target stacking sequence and ply-orientation are tabulated in table 1. Before tests all specimens are inspected using the X-radiography machine (HP 43855A) and C-scanning equipment (Vintek) to record initial flaws, if any. Impact tests are performed in the Impact Laboratory, National Cheng Kung University. The penetrator is launched by a pneumatic gun. Both normal and oblique impact tests, with an angle of obliquity(ϕ) equals to 0 or 15 degrees, are performed. A complete schematic representation of impact test setup is shown in figure 1. Current system is capable of firing a cylindrical conical tip-ended impactor, weighing 12.67 gm, up to 200 m/s. The penetrator, with a hardness of Rc 23, is made of steel rod. Figure 2 shows the geometry of penetrators used in tests. No permanent deformation of the impactor is observed in all tests. A pair of 5 mW He-Ne laser and diode sensor (UDT, pin5D), placed near the frontal surface of target, are used to measure elapse time for the penetrator cutting two laser lights in order to calculate initial impact speed.

A series of tests have been performed with an impact velocity ranging from 20 m/s up to 200 m/s. Impact damage on target is detected by using an optical camera, X-radiography equipments, and ultrasonic C-scanning facilities. In addition, a MTS 880 testing machine is used to conduct quasi-static tensile test in order to obtain load-displacement relationship and residual strength of the specimen. The cross-head speed of MTS system is set to be 0.12 inch per minute under stroke control mode (ASTM D3039-76) for all tests.

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A total of eighty tests have been performed at various impact velocities using two types of penetrators. Table 1 shows three kinds of specimens' layout using S-glass/epoxy pre-preg material. Three different types of specimens, i.e. $[0]_1^0_5$, $[0_5^0/90_5^0/0_5^0]$, and $[(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_5$

Figure 1 Schematic of the impact test (angle of impact obliquity (ϕ) = 15°).

Figure 2 Geometry of the impactors ($\theta = 45^\circ$)

laminates, are studied here. Both normal ($\phi = 0^\circ$) and oblique ($\phi = 15^\circ$) impact tests are conducted. The corresponding ballistic limits of these specimens found in tests are also tabulated in table 2 for each type of laminates. A summary of impact tests is shown in table 3 describing the types of impactor, stacking sequences, impact velocities, impact residual strength, and the perforation informations. The impact damages of specimens utilizing the non-destructive testing equipments have also been obtained to describe the damage patterns but not shown here.

Table 2 shows that in general the ballistic limit of all types of specimens increases as the mechanical behaviors of composite laminates become more isotropic, when a blunt impactor is used. We find that fibers along the longitudinal direction, i.e. 0° fibers, resist most of the impact momentum compared to those along other direction. This is the reason why the ballistic limit of a $[0_5^{\circ}/90_5^{\circ}/0_5^{\circ}]$ laminate is a little bit higher than that of a $[(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_S$ laminate when struck by a blunt penetrator. In the other way, the $[0_{15}^{\circ}]$ laminate has more plies containing 0° fibers but its ballistic limit is the lowest one among these three types of laminates. This is because that matrix cracks occurs in the $[0_{15}^{\circ}]$ laminate along 0° direction and break specimens into three pieces. This means that only about 1/3 of the specimen is resisting the impact momentum transferred from impactor.

If a tip-ended projectile is used, the ballistic limit will increase as the target's lay-up becomes more isotropic for normal and oblique impact tests, because the cross-link structures of fibers, such as $[0_5^{\circ}/90_5^{\circ}/0_5^{\circ}]$ and $[(0^{\circ}/\pm 45^{\circ}/90^{\circ})_2]_S$ laminates, are more efficient to stop tip-ended projectile. We also find that targets possess higher ballistic limit for those specimens which are struck by a blunt impactor. For normal impact, the ballistic limit of targets struck by a blunt impactor is about twice higher than those struck by a tip-ended impactor used here. The impact damages found in those specimens impacted by a blunt impactor are more severe than those using the tip-ended impactor. Moreover, the ballistic limit of oblique-impacted specimens struck by a blunt impactor is about 50 to 60 % higher than those using a tip-ended impactor. When we use blunt impactor to fire against the targets, the ballistic limit decreases 10 to 20 % for oblique impact tests. Although the penetration thickness, i.e. the length for impactor to go through the target in thickness direction, for an oblique impact is larger than a normal impact, but the angle of obliquity makes the blunt impactor possess the tip-ended impactor's characteristics and therefore decrease the ballistic limit. It is believed that the penetration thickness will have more influence on the thicker targets. On the other way, when we use the tip-ended penetrator and strike it on the target obliquely ($\phi = 15^{\circ}$), the ballistic limit then increases 10 to 20 % than those targets normally impacted by a tip-ended impactor.

The residual strength for all test specimens are tabulated in table 3. Figures 3(a) and (b) show the relations between the impact kinetic energy and the strength degradation ratio of an $[0_1^{\circ}5]$ impact damaged specimen and a $[0_1^{\circ}5]$ perfect specimen based on test results using blunt and tip-ended impactors, respectively. The Caprino's model^(16,17) is also used to fit strength degradation curves for normal and oblique impact test findings. The strength of a laminate containing a pre-drilled hole, with a diameter equivalent to impactor, using a MTS tester is also shown in the figures. When a blunt impactor with higher impact velocity fired normally against target as shown in figure 3(a). The residual strength of target is about 20% less than those struck obliquely based on the model suggested by Caprino and our test results. If a tip-ended impactor is used, the residual strength increases about 10% for the oblique impact test compared to a normal impact test as shown in Figure 3(b). However, for lower velocity impact tests the difference is less because the damages are small and limited in the area of contact.

The strength degradation ratio of $[0_5^{\circ}/90_5^{\circ}/0_5^{\circ}]$ laminates versus the impact energy of blunt and tip-ended impactors is shown in figures 4(a) and (b). Figure 4(a) shows that the oblique impact tests result in less impact damages globally and the strength degradation of specimens is less. Figure 4(b) shows that the strength degradation ratio is similar for normal and oblique tests.

The $[(0^{\circ}/\pm 45^{\circ}/90^{\circ})_2]_S$ laminates are also used as targets and the relation between strength degradation ratio versus impact energy is presented in figures 5(a) and (b). These two figures show that the degradation curves are more close to each other, because $[(0^{\circ}/\pm 45^{\circ}/90^{\circ})_2]_S$ laminates are more isotropic and less sensitive to the shapes of impactors. Based on above

descriptions, we know that the shapes of impactor, impact energy, target stacking sequences, and incidence angle of penetrators have significant influence on the impact strength degradation of composites. The corresponding damage patterns obtained using X-ray, C-scanning, and photographic facilities and the prediction of the residual strength and stress-strain behavior of impact damaged specimens is to be reported.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, impact residual strength of a S-glass/epoxy laminate subject to ballistic normal and oblique impact by a blunt or tip-ended penetrator are reported. Effects of the shape of penetrator, angle of obliquity, target stacking sequence, and impact momentum on the terminal ballistic limit and impact residual strength are important and can not be omitted. The specimen with pre-drilled hole can not simulate the case when target is perforated. The Caprino's model seems better fitted for the those tests where a tip-ended impactor is used and also for the oblique impact tests.

REFERENCES

- (1) J. L. Preston and T. S. Cook, "Impact Response of Graphite-Epoxy Flat Laminates Using Projectile that Simulate Aircraft Engine Encounters," ASTM STP 568, pp. 49-71, 1975.
- (2) N. Takeda, R. L. Sierakowski, and L. E. Malvern, "Experimental Impactor/Plate Configuration Interaction Studies of Impacted Glass Fiber-reinforced Composite Laminates", SAMPE quarterly, 12, pp. 9-17, 1981.
- (3) N. Takeda, R. L. Sierakowski, and L. E. Malvern, "Wave Propagation Experiments on Ballistically Impacted Composite Laminates," J. Composite Materials, v. 15, pp. 157-174, 1981.
- (4) S. P. Joshi and C. T. Sun, "Impact induced Fracture in a laminated composite", J. Composite Materials, v. 19, pp. 51-66, 1985.
- (5) C. T. Sun and S. Chattopadhyay, "Dynamic response of anisotropic laminated plates under initial stress to impact of a mass", J. Appl. Mech., v. 42, pp. 693-698, 1975.
- (6) N. Takeda, R. L. Sierakowski, C. A. Ross, and L. E. Malvern, "Delamination-Crack Propagation in Ballistically Impacted Glass/Epoxy Composite Laminates," Experimental Mechanics, v. 22, pp. 19-25, 1982.
- (7) N. Takeda, "Experimental Studies of the Delamination Mechanisms in Impacted Fiber-reinforced Composite Plates," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Florida, 1980.
- (8) F. K. Chang, H. Y. Choi, and S. T. Jenq, "Characterization of impact damage in laminated composites", SAMPE Journal, v. 26, pp. 18-25, 1990.
- (9) S. P. Joshi and C. T. Sun, "Impact induced fracture in a laminated composite", J. Composite Materials, v. 19, pp. 51-66, 1985.

- (10) W. J. Cantwell and J. Morton, "Detection of Impact Damage in CFRP Laminates," Composite Structures, v.3, pp. 241-257, 1985.
- (11) D. Liu, "Impact-Induced delamination - a view of bending stiffness mismatching", J. Composite Materials, v. 22, pp. 674-691, 1988.
- (12) D. A. Wyrick and D. F. Adams, "Residual strength of a carbon/epoxy composite material subjected to repeated impact", J. Composite Materials, v. 22, pp. 749-765, 1988.
- (13) S. R. Swanson and H. G. Rezaee, "Strength loss in composites from lateral contact loads", Composite Sci. and Tech., v. 38, pp. 43-54, 1990.
- (14) J. A. Suarez and J. B. Whiteside, "Comparison of Residual Strength of Composite and Metal Structures After Ballistic Damage," ASTM STP 568, pp. 72-91, 1975.
- (15) G. E. Husman, J. M. Whitney, and J. C. Halpin, "Residual Strength Characterization of Laminated Composites Subjected to Impact Loading," ASTM STP 568, pp. 92-113, 1975.
- (16) G. Caprino, "Residual Strength Prediction of Impacted GFRP Laminates," J. Composite Materials, v. 18, pp 508-518, 1984.
- (17) G. Caprino, "On the prediction of residual strength for notched laminates", J. Material Science, v. 18, pp. 2269-2273, 1983.

stacking sequence	number of plies
$[0_{15}]$	15
$[0_5/90_5/0_5]$	15
$[(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_s$	16

Table 1 Stacking sequence of the test specimens.

laminates lay-up	ballistic		limit (m/s)	
	normal	impact	oblique	impact
	blunt impactor*	tip-ended impactor**	blunt impactor*	tip-ended impactor**
$[0_{15}]$	100 - 110	40 - 50	80 - 90	55 - 65
$[0_5/90_5/0_5]$	110 - 120	50 - 60	95 - 105	65 - 75
$[(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_2]_s$	110 - 120	60 - 70	85 - 95	70 - 80

* specimen impacted by a cylindrical flat-ended projector.

** specimen impacted by a cylindrical conical projector.

Table 2 The ballistic limit of composite specimens.

Test No.	Impactor ¹	Stacking sequence	Impact velocity (m/s)	Impact momentum (kg m/s)	Residual strength (GPa)	Note ²
A1(FE00)	flat-end ($\phi = 0^\circ$)	[0 ₁₅] ^o	0	0	1.652	
A2(FE02)	"	"	23.47	0.338	1.537	n.p.
A3(FE11)	"	"	34.	0.490	1.388	"
A4(FE22)	"	"	42.13	0.608	1.333	"
A5(FE33)	"	"	48.74	0.703	1.254	"
A6(FE66)	"	"	108.7	1.57	-	p.
A7(FE88)	"	"	122.	1.76	-	"
A8(FE99)	"	"	138.	1.99	0.327	"
B1(FF04)	tip-end ($\phi = 0^\circ$)	[0 ₁₅] ^o	23.82	0.30	1.650	n.p.
B2(FF01)	"	"	33.80	0.43	1.321	"
B3(FF02)	"	"	54.88	0.70	1.246	p.
B4(FF03)	"	"	73.75	0.93	0.948	"
B5(FF05)	"	"	113.4	1.44	0.827	"
C1(TE00)	flat-end ($\phi = 0^\circ$)	[0 ₅ /90 ₅ /0 ₅] ^o	0	0	1.284	
C2(TE01)	"	"	27.26	0.39	1.202	n.p.
C3(TE05)	"	"	35.40	0.51	1.117	"
C4(TE07)	"	"	48.6	0.70	0.988	"
C5(TE11)	"	"	60.38	0.88	0.841	"
C6(TE88)	"	"	112.70	1.63	-	"
C7(TE77)	"	"	121.37	1.75	-	p.
C8(TE99)	"	"	140.0	2.02	0.372	"
D1(TF00)	tip-end ($\phi = 0^\circ$)	[0 ₅ /90 ₅ /0 ₅] ^o	0	0	1.284	
D2(TF01)	"	"	23.26	0.29	1.108	n.p.
D3(TF03)	"	"	35.17	0.44	1.040	"
D4(TF04)	"	"	50.70	0.63	0.903	"
D5(TF05)	"	"	70.50	0.88	0.707	p.
D6(TF06)	"	"	109.51	1.37	0.725	"
E1(GE00)	flat-end ($\phi = 0^\circ$)	[(0 ^o / $\pm 45^\circ$ /90 ^o) ₂] _s	0	0	0.554	
E2(GE01)	"	"	24.16	0.35	0.534	n.p.
E3(GE02)	"	"	32.94	0.47	0.535	"
E4(GE06)	"	"	48.32	0.7	0.366	"
E5(GE07)	"	"	61.2	0.88	0.250	"
E6(GE88)	"	"	103.	1.49	-	"
E7(GE77)	"	"	114.52	1.66	-	p.
E8(GE99)	"	"	141.20	2.04	0.238	"
F1(GF02)	tip-end ($\phi = 0^\circ$)	[(0 ^o / $\pm 45^\circ$ /90 ^o) ₂] _s	28.12	0.36	0.510	n.p.
F2(GF05)	"	"	43.75	0.55	0.376	"
F3(GF06)	"	"	59.22	0.75	0.304	"
F4(GF07)	"	"	77.31	0.98	0.233	p.
F5(GF08)	"	"	115.31	1.46	0.243	"
G1(FA15-1)	flat-end ($\phi = 15^\circ$)	[0 ₁₅] ^o	26.34	0.379	1.540	n.p.
G2(FA15-2)	"	"	37.43	0.539	1.326	"
G3(FA15-3)	"	"	48.48	0.698	-	"
G4(FA15-4)	"	"	54.70	0.788	0.876	"
G5(FA15-5)	"	"	74.42	1.072	-	"
G6(FA15-6)	"	"	87.67	1.262	0.713	p.
G7(FA15-7)	"	"	112.28	1.617	0.665	"

H1(TA15-1)	tip-end ($\phi = 15^\circ$)	$[0_{15}]$	26.89	0.344	1.599	n.p.
H2(TA15-2)	"	"	34.41	0.440	1.519	"
H3(TA15-3)	"	"	56.64	0.725	1.316	"
H4(TA15-4)	"	"	62.71	0.802	1.235	p.
H5(TA15-5)	"	"	82.05	1.050	1.173	"
H6(TA15-6)	"	"	116.36	1.489	0.898	"
I1(F15-1)	flat-end ($\phi = 15^\circ$)	$[0_5/90_5/0_5]$	24.52	0.353	1.230	n.p.
I2(F15-2)	"	"	37.83	0.545	1.088	"
I3(F15-3)	"	"	58.97	0.849	0.937	"
I4(F15-4)	"	"	87.69	1.263	0.740	"
I5(F15-5)	"	"	98.70	1.421	-	"
I6(F15-6)	"	"	106.67	1.536	0.482	p.
J1(T15-1)	tip-end ($\phi = 15^\circ$)	$[0_5/90_5/0_5]$	26.67	0.341	1.095	n.p.
J2(T15-2)	"	"	42.33	0.542	1.055	"
J3(T15-3)	"	"	46.47	0.595	0.994	"
J4(T15-4)	"	"	62.87	0.805	0.808	"
J5(T15-5)	"	"	70.66	0.904	0.766	p.
J6(T15-6)	"	"	103.01	1.319	0.727	"
K1(FF15-1)	flat-end ($\phi = 15^\circ$)	$[(0_{\pm 45}/90_2)_s]$	26.12	0.376	0.539	n.p.
K2(FF15-2)	"	"	40.00	0.576	0.474	"
K3(FF15-3)	"	"	42.67	0.614	-	"
K4(FF15-4)	"	"	44.14	0.636	0.430	"
K5(FF15-5)	"	"	64.00	0.922	0.297	"
K6(FF15-6)	"	"	98.46	1.418	0.204	p.
K7(FF15-7)	"	"	85.33	1.229	-	"
K8(FF15-8)	"	"	110.34	1.589	0.183	"
L1(TF15-1)	tip-end ($\phi = 15^\circ$)	$[(0_{\pm 45}/90_2)_s]$	24.71	0.316	0.489	n.p.
L2(TF15-2)	"	"	40.00	0.512	0.409	"
L3(TF15-3)	"	"	53.33	0.683	0.321	"
L4(TF15-4)	"	"	67.37	0.862	-	"
L5(TF15-5)	"	"	75.29	0.964	0.299	p.
L6(TF15-6)	"	"	85.33	1.092	-	"
L7(TF15-7)	"	"	116.36	1.489	0.233	"

¹ Flat-end and tip-ended the cylindrical flat-ended penetrator (14.42 gm) and cylindrical conical tipped-end penetrator (12.67 gm), respectively.

² Symbol 'p.' and 'n.p.' represent perforation and no perforation, respectively.

Table 3 Summary of the impact tests.

Figure 3 Strength degradation ratio versus impact energy of $[0_{15}]$ laminates struck by (a) blunt or (b) tip-ended impactor.

Figure 4 Strength degradation ratio versus impact energy of $[0_5/90_5/0_5]$ laminates struck by (a) blunt or (b) tip-ended impactor.

Figure 5 Strength degradation ratio versus impact energy of $[(0/+45/90)_2]_s$ laminates struck by (a) blunt or (b) tip-ended impactor.

